

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF THE HANDS TEST TO MEASURE ROTATION ABILITY WITH MENTAL IMAGERY (RAMI-HANDS TEST), A NEW MENTAL ROTATION TEST

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Resumen

La capacidad espacial es la habilidad para visualizar y manipular mentalmente las relaciones entre los objetos y el espacio; sin embargo, esta capacidad no es unitaria y se puede distinguir hasta cinco componentes en la capacidad espacial. Este estudio se centra en la capacidad espacial de la rotación mental, que implica la capacidad de rotar rápidamente y con precisión figuras. Para ello, se ha diseñado un test “the Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands Test)”, que consta de 18 ítems relacionados con imágenes de manos en distintas posiciones. Además, se ha estudiado la fiabilidad, mediante la alfa de Cronbach, y la validez de RAMI-Hands Test, mediante la correlación de Pearson con distintas pruebas de imágenes mentales. Los participantes fueron 219 estudiantes de universidad que cubrieron varias pruebas relacionadas con habilidad espacial, control de imagen y viveza de imagen. Los análisis estadísticos indicaron que RAMI-Hands Test tiene una adecuada fiabilidad y validez. Consideramos que la sencillez de la prueba la hace adecuada para un rango amplio de población, evitando la dificultad que conlleva las figuras geométricas en 3D y la falta de experiencia con dichas figuras. Futuros estudios deberían ir dirigidos a individuos con distintos rangos de edad, distintas titulaciones y diferentes ámbitos para así fortalecer nuestros resultados.

Palabras clave: rotación mental, imagen espacial, test, imágenes mentales.

Abstract

Spatial ability is the skill to visualize and mentally manipulate the relationships between objects and space; however, this ability is not unitary and up to five components can be distinguished within it. This study focuses on the spatial ability of mental rotation, which involves the capacity to rotate figures quickly and accurately. For this purpose, a test was designed: the Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands Test), consisting of 18 items related to images of hands in different positions. In addition, the reliability of the RAMI-Hands Test was studied using Cronbach's alpha, and its validity was assessed through Pearson's correlation with different mental imagery tests. The participants were 219 university students who completed several tests related to spatial ability, image control, and image vividness. Statistical analyses indicated that the RAMI-Hands Test has adequate reliability and validity. We consider that the simplicity of the test makes it suitable for a wide range of populations, avoiding the difficulty posed by 3D geometric figures and the lack of experience with such figures. Future studies should be directed towards individuals of different age ranges, academic degrees, and fields in order to strengthen our results.

Keywords: rotation mental, spatial imagery, test, mental imagery.

Introduction

Spatial ability is the skill to visualize and mentally manipulate the relationships between objects and space (Bartlett et al., 2024; Shepard & Metzler, 1971). Researchers do not consider spatial ability to be a single skill, and “spatial ability” or “spatial abilities” are better understood as umbrella terms that encompass different visual and mental processes, which are categorized in various ways by different researchers (Carroll, 1993). According to Maier (1996), spatial ability can be divided into five components. Spatial perception, which is the ability to see objects from a vertical or horizontal point of view. Spatial visualization, which includes the ability to visualize a configuration in which there is movement or displacement between (internal) parts of the configuration. Mental rotation, which involves the ability to rotate 2D or 3D figures quickly and accurately. Spatial relations, referring to the ability to understand the spatial arrangement of objects or parts of an object and their relationship to one another. And spatial orientation, which involves the ability to orient oneself physically or mentally in space.

Uttal et al. (2013) proposed a framework that groups spatial skills using two distinctions: the use of intrinsic versus extrinsic information, and the nature of the task as static versus dynamic. Intrinsic information refers to the details and relationships between parts that define a specific object, whereas extrinsic information relates to the positions of objects in relation to each other. Other researchers have used different categorizations, for example, grouping small-scale tasks related to shape manipulation separately from large-scale tasks such as understanding the layout of a building (Atit et al., 2020). Another categorization, more focused on tasks occurring in spatial assessments involving drawings rather than real-world objects, divided spatial skills based on whether they involved manipulations only in a two-dimensional (2D) plane or in three dimensions (3D) (Eliot & Smith, 1983).

Researchers often use psychometric instruments to assess spatial ability (Gorska & Sorby, 2008). Most psychometric instruments are multiple-choice tests that use line drawings of shapes in black and white (Eliot & Smith, 1983). These psychometric tests are considered to assess fundamental spatial skills (Atit et al., 2020). Spatial ability assessment has been used to predict success in science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) careers. Researchers from a broad range of STEM disciplines, including geology, physics, chemistry, mathematics, and engineering, have consistently underscored the critical role that spatial reasoning plays in the advancement and practice of their respective fields (Atit et al., 2020; Delage et al., 2024; Hegarty & Waller, 2005; Uttal et al., 2024).

Current studies advocate for the development of spatial skills to enhance students' success in STEM disciplines (Hawes et al., 2022; Sorby et al., 2018), and to help improve equity and diversity in STEM, including addressing the gender gap (Tian et al., 2022). Moreover, as suggested by Uttal et al. (2013), training spatial skills at educational levels prior to university could encourage an increase in the choice of STEM-related careers.

The most commonly used tests to measure spatial rotation are related to three-dimensional geometric objects presented in two dimensions, usually on paper (Bartlett et al., 2024). Uttal et al. (2024) identify various limitations of spatial tests used in research and highlight the need to create new tests that can be used across a broader range of populations and contexts, due to the difficulty faced by individuals whose experience is not related to the spatial perception of three-dimensional geometric objects. Thus, different studies have highlighted differences in spatial rotation performance among students from various grades (Campos & Campos-Juanatey, 2019a, b; Pérez-Fabello et al., 2016, 2018). Architecture and engineering students have extensive experience in three-dimensional visualization with geometric objects and image rotation, and their performance is much higher compared to other students, such as those in fine arts or psychology (Pérez-Fabello et al., 2016, 2018).

This study aimed to create a simple test of spatial rotation, the Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands Test). This test avoids the difficulties of using 3D geometric figures represented on paper inherent in traditional psychometric tests, as noted by Bartlett et al. (2024). To that end, a test was designed in which the object to be rotated would pose no visualization difficulty, using a 2D paper representation and a flat rotation movement, similar to that of clock hands. In this way, the difficulties of visualizing 3D geometric figures are avoided and differences in prior experience with such figures are reduced. Additionally, the validity and reliability of the test were also examined.

Method

Participants

A total of 219 undergraduate students from the Fine Arts program at the University of Vigo, Spain (49 men and 170 women; $M = 21$ years, $SD = 4.89$; age range: 18–38 years), participated in this study.

Materials

The Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands Test) was

developed to assess mental image rotation ability and consists of 18 items involving images of hands in different positions (see full test in Appendix 1). Each item presents a model image and four similar images rotated in space: two match the model's orientation, and two are mirror-inverted versions. Participants are required to identify the two images that are identical to the model and circle the correct answers. To do so, they must mentally rotate each option. Individual scores are calculated by adding the number of correct responses and subtracting the number of incorrect ones (unanswered items are not counted). Therefore, total scores can range from -36 to 36. (The correct answers for each item are as follows: 1 [A, D], 2 [B, C], 3 [B, D], 4 [A, C], 5 [B, C], 6 [A, D], 7 [A, B], 8 [B, C], 9 [A, C], 10 [B, D], 11 [A, B], 12 [B, C], 13 [A, D], 14 [B, D], 15 [A, C], 16 [B, D], 17 [A, C], 18 [A, B].) Participants were given one and a half minutes to complete the test.

The Measure of the Ability to Form Spatial Mental Imagery (MASMI; Campos, 2009, 2013). This test consists of a decomposed cube that participants must mentally fold in order to answer each of the 23 questions. Each question includes four response options, two of which are correct and two incorrect. The total score is calculated by adding correct answers and subtracting incorrect ones, resulting in a possible score range from -46 to 46. Participants are given 5 minutes to complete all items. Campos (2009, 2012) reported Cronbach's alpha coefficients of .93 and .90, respectively.

Spatial Scale of the Primary Mental Abilities Test (PMA) (Thurstone & Thurstone, 1962, 2002). This test measures the ability to imagine and mentally manipulate objects in two or three dimensions. It consists of 20 items, each presenting a flat geometric model alongside six similar figures. Participants must determine which of the six figures match the model, even if they have been rotated within the same plane. The time limit for the test is 5 minutes. A Cronbach's alpha of .93 was reported by Thurstone and Thurstone (2002), and a value of .89 was obtained by Ramírez-Uclés and Ramírez-Uclés (2020).

The Mental Rotation Test (MRT; Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978). This test comprises 10 items designed to measure the ability to mentally rotate objects. Each item includes a model and four options, two correct and two incorrect. Participants are given 3 minutes to mentally rotate the figures to determine if they match the model. Vandenberg and Kuse (1978) recommend scoring each item with two points if both correct options are selected, zero points if one or both are incorrect, and one point if only one correct option is selected. The total score ranges from 0 to 20. Test-retest reliability was reported as .83 by Vandenberg and Kuse (1978), and Cronbach's alpha was .72 according to Rahe and Quaiser-Pohl (2019).

Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020) of the Plymouth Sensory Imagery Questionnaire (Psi-Q; Andrade et al., 2014). This version consists of 35 items measuring the vividness of mental imagery across seven sensory modalities: vision, sound, smell, taste, touch, bodily sensation, and emotional feeling. There are five items per modality, each rated on a 7-point scale ranging from 1 (no image) to 7 (as vivid as real life). The visual modality refers to appearance (e.g., “a cat climbing a tree”); the auditory modality begins with “imagine the sound of...” (e.g., “hands clapping in applause”); the olfactory modality with “imagine the smell of...” (e.g., “a rose”); the gustatory modality with “imagine the taste of...” (e.g., “lemon”); the tactile modality with “imagine touching...” (e.g., “icy water”); the bodily sensation modality with “imagine the bodily sensation of...” (e.g., “relaxing in a warm bath”); and the emotional feeling modality with “imagine feeling...” (e.g., “in love”). The Cronbach’s alpha for the Psi-Q was .92 (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020).

Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire (VVIQ; Marks, 1973). We used the Spanish version of the test (Campos et al., 2002). The questionnaire consists of 16 items, completed twice: once with eyes open and once with eyes closed. An example item is: “Visualize a rising sun... The sun is rising above the horizon into a hazy sky.” Each item is rated from 1 (perfectly clear image, as vivid as real experience) to 5 (no image at all, only a knowing of what one is thinking about). Thus, higher scores on the VVIQ indicate lower vividness, and lower scores indicate higher vividness. Campos et al. (2002) reported a Cronbach’s alpha of .88.

Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2004) of the Gordon Test of Visual Imagery Control (Gordon Test; Richardson, 1969). This test assesses individuals’ ability to control visual images and consists of 12 items asking participants to imagine a car in various colors, positions, and motion states. Participants then rate each response on a 3-point scale: “no” (0 points), “unsure” (1 point), and “yes” (2 points). The total score ranges from 0 to 24, with higher scores indicating greater imagery control. Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2004) reported a Cronbach’s alpha of .69.

Procedure

Participants, who were second-year undergraduate students in the Fine Arts program at the University of Vigo, completed the following questionnaires at their usual classrooms, in groups of approximately 20 students: the Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery

(RAMI-Hands Test), the Measure of the Ability to Form Spatial Mental Imagery (MASMI; Campos, 2009, 2013), the Spatial Scale of the Primary Mental Abilities Test (PMA; Thurstone & Thurstone, 1962/2002), the Mental Rotation Test (MRT; Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978), the Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020) of the Plymouth Sensory Imagery Questionnaire (Psi-Q; Andrade et al., 2014), the Spanish version (Campos et al., 2002) of the Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire (VVIQ; Marks, 1973), and the Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2004) of the Gordon Test of Visual Imagery Control (Gordon Test; Richardson, 1969). The order of test administration was counterbalanced.

All students were assured that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential, and written informed consent was obtained from each individual. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki. Approval was obtained from the University of Vigo's Ethics Committee (Ref. 0025-F-2024-03-08).

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 25.0 and IBM SPSS Amos 25. The internal consistency of the tests was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Descriptive statistics were calculated for all measures, and finally, Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficients were used to examine the relationships between the RAMI-Hands Test and the other imagery measures.

Results and Discussion

First, we analyzed the reliability of the tests used. The internal consistency of the RAMI-Hands Test, as measured by Cronbach's alpha, was .87. According to George and Mallery (2003) and Oviedo and Campo-Arias (2005), this level of internal consistency is considered high and indicates that the test has "good" reliability. The Cronbach's α values for the other tests were as follows: MASMI obtained $\alpha = .86$, slightly lower than the .93 reported by Campos (2009, 2013) and the .92 obtained by Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2023a). The PMA showed $\alpha = .90$, which is consistent with previous findings: .93 (Thurstone & Thurstone, 2002) and .89 (Ramírez-Uclés & Ramírez-Uclés, 2020). The MRT yielded $\alpha = .80$, which is close to the .83 reported in the original study by Vandenberg and Kuse (1978). The Psi-Q showed $\alpha = .95$, similar to the .92 reported in the Spanish version by Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2020). The VVIQ obtained $\alpha = .93$, slightly higher than the .88 reported by Campos et al. (2002). Finally, the Gordon Test yielded $\alpha = .69$, the same as in Pérez-Fabello (2004), and comparable to the .68 reported by Pérez-Fabello (2023a)

and the .71 reported by Pérez-Fabello (2023b). As can be seen, the tests used in this study demonstrated good internal consistency, generally falling within the recommended range of .70 to .90 (Oviedo & Campo-Arias, 2005). Descriptive statistics for the measures used in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Descriptive Statistics for the Measures Used in Study

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Minimum	Maximum
RAMI-Hands Test	18.21	7.16	1	36
MASMI	12.33	9.14	0	44
MRT	9.86	5.22	0	20
PMA	27.64	12.30	0	54
Gordon Test	21.47	2.89	12	24
VVIQ	2.09	0.59	1.06	4.63
Psi-Q	5.45	0.90	1,26	7

The Pearson product-moment correlations between the RAMI-Hands Test and the other mental imagery measures are presented in Table 2. As shown in Table 2, the RAMI-Hands Test was significantly correlated with the MASMI, a test that measures image rotation. Significant correlations were also found between the RAMI-Hands Test and the MRT, as well as between the RAMI-Hands Test and the PMA. Previous studies have reported similar correlations between spatial rotation tests (e.g., Blajenkova et al., 2006; Burton & Fogarty, 2003; Campos, 2009; Kozhevnikov et al., 2002; Poltrock & Brown, 1984; Richardson, 1977).

The correlation between the RAMI-Hands Test and the imagery questionnaires (Gordon Test, VVIQ, and Psi-Q) (see Table 2) was low and non-significant, which is consistent with the findings of other studies examining the relationship between spatial tests and the aforementioned imagery vividness questionnaires (e.g., Blajenkova et al., 2006; Burton & Fogarty, 2003; Campos, 2009; Poltrock & Brown, 1984; Richardson, 1977). Our findings indicate that the RAMI-Hands Test demonstrates high reliability. Its validity is comparable to that observed in other spatial tests and aligns with expectations based on imagery vividness measures.

Table 2.

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlations between the RAMI-Hands Test and the Other Measures of Imagery

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. RAMI-Hands Test						
2. MASMI	.36*					
3. MRT	.34*	.52*				
4. PMA	.55*	.51*	.56*			
5. Gordon Test	-.07	-.09	-.02	-.05		
6. VVIQ	.12	.12	-.03	.09	-.38*	
7 Psi-Q	.02	-.06	-.12	.05	.28*	-.39*

* $p < .001$.

The main limitation of this study is that it was conducted exclusively with university students. Therefore, further research is needed to confirm our findings and to explore the applicability of the test across different populations. We believe that the simplicity of the test makes it suitable for a wide range of individuals, as it avoids the challenges associated with 3D geometric figures and the lack of experience with such stimuli—an issue particularly relevant for individuals less familiar with these types of tasks, as noted by Bartlett et al. (2024). Moreover, the test may also be appropriate for a broader age range, including both younger and older participants.

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Appendix

Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands)

This test measures the ability to mentally rotate objects in space. Each item consists of a model image and four response options. The task is to mentally rotate each response option—either in a clockwise or counterclockwise direction—and determine which ones match the model exactly. There are always two correct answers and two incorrect ones.

Take a look at the example. If we mentally rotate option A, we will see that it matches the model exactly. Option B, no matter how we rotate it—forward or backward—does not match the model. Option C, when mentally rotated, also matches the model. Finally, option D does not match the model when rotated. The correct answers are A and C; therefore, you should draw a circle around these two options.

MODEL	OPTION	OPTION	OPTION	OPTION
example	(A)	B	(C)	D

Your total score will reflect both correct and incorrect answers. Therefore, do not guess unless you have some idea that your choice is correct.

The previous item was just an example. Now the actual test will begin. As soon as you are instructed to do so, turn the page over and try to answer all the questions as quickly as possible. If you finish the first page, continue with the next one. You will have one and a half minutes to complete the test.

If you find a question too difficult, skip it and move on to the next one. If you have time left at the end, you may go back to it. Keep in mind that a response figure matches the model only when; after mentally rotating it, it overlaps and aligns with the model exactly.

DO NOT TURN THE PAGE UNTIL YOU ARE TOLD TO DO SO.

MODEL	OPTION	OPTION	OPTION	OPTION
<p>D</p>				
<p>D</p>				
<p>D</p>				
<p>D</p>				
<p>D</p>				
<p>D</p>				

END